

ISSN Print: 2394-7500
ISSN Online: 2394-5869
Impact Factor: 5.2
IJAR 2019; 5(7): 143-145
www.allresearchjournal.com
Received: 01-05-2019
Accepted: 03-06-2019

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Social adjustment of ix standard students: Familial variables wise analysis

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Abstract

In the present study, an attempt has been made to study the social adjustment of IX standard students with regard to familial variables namely, mothers' education, fathers' education, mothers' occupation and fathers' occupation. Normative survey method was followed. The sample data were captured from a population of IX standard students in the schools of Kovilpatti Taluk, Thoothukudi district. The participants selected through simple random sampling method including 300 IX standard students. Questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection. Social adjustment scale developed by the investigator (2018) was used to measure social adjustment of IX standard students. Chi-square test was adopted to test the hypothesis under study, at 0.05 level of significance. The current study findings revealed that there is no significant difference in social adjustment of IX standard students with regard to familial variables namely, mothers' education, fathers' education, mothers' occupation and fathers' occupation.

Keywords: Social adjustment, familial variable, IX standard students

Introduction

Man as a social being not only adapts to physical demands but he also adjusts to social pressures in the society. The term adjustment is broadly used for varying conditions of social or interpersonal relations in the society whereby adjustment means reaction to the demands and pressures of social environment imposed upon the individual. The demand may be external or internal to whom the individual has to react. Just as biological adjustment is needed for physical survival of the organism, social adjustment is needed for individual growth, gratification and success in life. It is in this sense that adjustment becomes a process of learning [6]. Students who fail to attain a satisfactory level of social adjustment will have difficulties in school. As a matter of fact, the development of healthy personality is largely determined by the way in which the individual is able to make adjustment in his life. It is in this sense that the very concept of personality is defined in terms of the individual's process of dynamic organization of his psycho-physical systems for effective and unique adjustment to the environment. A growing child has to successfully effect adjustment in various aspects of his life like home, health, personal, academic, emotional, social, school, vacation and so on. Hurlock (1955) recognized the period of adjustment and says that it is a period of maturing. A balanced personality is the outcome of proper adjustment of an individual of his social environment [3]. The school period is synonymous with the ability to adapt to the social environment, where when students are able to adapt well to their daily lives they will enjoy. Basically, the social adjustment is an adaptability that is considered an important attribute in society. When students have good or bad social adjustment will greatly affect some things, namely, aggressive behaviour, coping ability in handling problems, moral values that exist in him, to the academic value of these students [5]. The primary source of growth, development and socialization during childhood is the family; One of the family is the preparation of its children for adult roles [7]. Akpan, Idiok, Paulina & Aniebietabasi Ackley (2018). found that there is a significant influence of family type on student's social development ($P > 0.05$). Family structure significantly influence student's social adjustment [1]. So the family structure may play a vital role in social adjustment of a child. But Priya Packiaselvi and Malathi (2017) found that there is no significant difference towards social adjustment based educational qualification of father, educational qualification of mother, monthly income of father, monthly income of mother, type of family [4].

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So the family background may not be influence the social adjustment of students. Babita Arora (2016) [2] found that the coefficient of correlation between social dimension of adjustment and parental involvement of adolescents of working and non-working parents as 0.25 which is positive and significant at .01 level of confidence. This indicates that a significant positive relationship exist between social dimension of adjustment and parental involvement among adolescents of working and non-working parents [3].

Methodology and instrumentation

Normative survey method was followed. The sample data were captured from a population of IX standard students in the schools of Kovilpatti Taluk, Thoothukudi district. The participants selected through simple random sampling method including 300 IX standard students. Questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection. Social adjustment scale developed by the investigator (2018) was used to measure social adjustment of IX standard students. Chi-square test was adopted to test the hypothesis under study, at 0.05 level of significance.

Objectives of the study

To find out whether there is any significant difference in social adjustment of IX standard students with regard to familial variables namely,

- Mothers’ education
- Fathers’ education
- Mothers’ occupation
- Fathers’ occupation

Hypotheses of the study

- There is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ education of IX standard students.
- There is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers’ education of IX standard students.
- There is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ occupation of IX standard students.
- There is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers’ occupation of IX standard students.

Analysis of data

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ education of IX standard students.

Table 1: Chi-square test showing the significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ education of IX standard students

Variable	Mother’s Education	df	Calculated value of χ^2	Table value of χ^2	Remarks at 5% level
Social Adjustment	Illiterate	4	1.614	9.49	NS*
	School level				
	College level				

(* Not significant at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that calculated ‘ χ^2 ’ value (1.614) is less than the table value (9.49) for df (4) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ education of IX standard

students.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers’ education of IX standard students.

Table 2: Chi-square test showing the significant association between social adjustment and fathers’ education of IX standard students

Variable	Father’s Education	df	Calculated value of χ^2	Table value of χ^2	Remarks at 5% level
Social Adjustment	Illiterate	4	2.165	9.49	NS*
	School level				
	College level				

(* Not significant at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that calculated ‘ χ^2 ’ value (2.165) is less than the table value (9.49) for df (4) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers’ education of IX standard students.

Null Hypothesis 3: There is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ occupation of IX standard students.

Table 3: Chi-square test showing the significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ occupation of IX standard students

Variable	Mother’s Occupation	df	Calculated value of χ^2	Table value of χ^2	Remarks at 5% level
Social Adjustment	Coolie	4	3.164	9.49	NS*
	Government				
	Private				

(* Not significant at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that calculated ‘ χ^2 ’ value (3.164) is less than the table value (9.49) for df (4) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

It shows that there is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers’ occupation of IX standard students.

Null Hypothesis 4: There is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers' occupation of IX standard students.

Table 4: Chi-square test showing the significant association between social adjustment and fathers' occupation of IX standard students

Variable	Father's Occupation	df	Calculated value of χ^2	Table value of χ^2	Remarks at 5% level
Social Adjustment	Coolie	4	1.095	9.49	NS*
	Government				
	Private				

(* Not significant at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that calculated ' χ^2 ' value (3.164) is less than the table value (9.49) for df (4) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers' occupation of IX standard students.

Findings of the study

- There is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers' education of IX standard students.
- There is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers' education of IX standard students.
- There is no significant association between social adjustment and mothers' occupation of IX standard students.
- There is no significant association between social adjustment and fathers' occupation of IX standard students.

Conclusion

After the analysis of the result, it was found that there is no significant difference in social adjustment of IX standard students with regard to familial variables namely, mothers' education, fathers' education, mothers' occupation and fathers' occupation which indicated that all the groups with regard to familial variables have similar level of social adjustment. It explicit that the familial variables namely mothers' education, fathers' education, mothers' occupation and fathers' occupation are not influence the social adjustment of IX standard students.

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